

ANALYSIS OF EXPORT CIRCULATION OF FIRMS AND COMPANIES

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Abstract: The burning and development of economic activity on the road is taken as one of the main directions in economic activity. One of the most important and effective aspects of the activities of enterprises is to engage in economic activity and become an active participant of the world market. From this point of view, it is important to draw up a state program for the establishment of economic activity on the road and the determination of economic and legal foundations in this regard.

Keywords: economic activity, effective aspects, world market.

As we know, one of the indicators that represent the effectiveness of enterprises is its operation without damage. This, in turn, consists in the production of high-quality and competitive products, without increasing the cost of production due to the effective cost-effective use of production tools, cocktails and raw materials resources.

The task of the head of any enterprise is to correctly select the cost of selling a product, reduce costs, find production reserves, develop expenses, find the optimal level of cost, make a rational decision on the effective use of production reserves. If they cannot predict in the future on the basis of clear and convincing data on the state in which income and losses will be divided, it is impossible to achieve efficiency in making management decisions. For this reason, the growth of production, the determination of revenue, cost and net profit from sales will have to be based on the fact that production will work without loss. This means that it is

important to minimize the material costs spent on production at high profits of enterprises and at the same time sell the products created by them at high prices.

The main purpose of our coverage of this topic is to study the analysis of export circulation of firms and companies from theoretical and practical skills. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To get acquainted with the economic and economic bases of burning of Tashki economic activity on Yul and the issues of its development in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2. Study of the content and significance of the Taxal of economic activity.

3. Implementation of the evacuation of export operations.

4. Acquaintance with the tax of income and expenses from escort import operations.

Economic and social development of the country cannot be imagined without external economic activity. This, in turn, requires communication and cooperation with foreign countries in various spheres of activity, determining the possible conditions for entering the arena of the world market for products and services and taking a place in it.

Today, the development and prospects of economic relations with foreign countries in our Republic can be positively assessed. Because in recent years, joint ventures and joint ventures of various forms of ownership have been established. Today, most of them are actively working.

These enterprises are mainly focused on the internal consumption of the republic. But we are able to use all the possible conditions of economic opportunities and legal criteria. Because more than 40 percent of the established and registered existing enterprises are still in operation. Some of them are in the process of re-registration and changing the form of activity, some of them are still able to carry out their activities.

Here are the cocktail resources. Currently, there are about 8 million people in our republic who are working. Most of them are engaged in agriculture. Almost 60

percent of the available production resources are employed in the agriculture and service industries. The relative abundance of Work resources is extremely high. This greatly affects their effective use. The relative surplus of labor resources characterizes the fact that there is more than usual employment in the economy of our Republic. This employment has an active influence on their quality and regeneration.

The excess of available labor resources has finally lowered the market value of the labor force that is paid to them. In foreign economic activity, the cheapness of labor resources is taken as an important factor. Of course, great work has been done and is still being done on legal grounds.

Analysis of external economic activity is studied separately as an important part of economic analysis. In foreign economic activity, we consider analysis as an important condition of management and action. Based on the analysis, the organizational forms of the enterprise's external economic activity, changes in the export and import of products and services, the factors affecting its changes, the structure of the export and import of goods, the sale and purchase of goods on credit terms, the changes in income and expenses from export and import operations. to determine the factors influencing the change in profit, to determine the internal opportunities available in the enterprise in order to increase the foreign trade turnover of the enterprise and the measures to implement them, to draw up and implement technical projects for the implementation of cooperation, to make a brief diagnosis and comment on the external economic activity of the enterprise The content of the analysis of external economic activity.

Two indicators in the general case are taken as comparable important indicators.

1. Export volume
2. Import volume

According to the analysis of export operations, the volume of products and services sold in the foreign trade turnover and their changes compared to the two previous years are evaluated. The important part is the export volume of the society.

Factor analysis of the volume of imports and its changes is considered as an important part of the analysis. Quantitative and qualitative factors influencing the change in export volume are studied.

An indicator with a quantitative expression is taken as a quantitative factor. As a quality factor, the change of indicators characterizing the important economic efficiency of the enterprise is taken.

In the analysis of import operations, attention is paid to the implementation of the plan and its dynamics, composition, structure, income and expenses from import operations, the profitability of import operations, and the analysis of factors affecting the import volume.

Changes in the volume of imported goods, as well as changes in the price of imported goods, can be included as factors affecting the change in the volume of imports.

In the analysis, important attention is also paid to evaluating the goods taken on credit and their weight in the total volume of imports.

Table-1
Analysis of the implementation of the foreign trade turnover plan

Indicators	Plan		Plan		Gross size		Executi on of the plan
	Amo unt	Evaluat ion	Amo unt	Evaluat ion	Amount	Evalua tion	
A- the product	100	5000	120	6000	50	72	144,0
B- the product	80	3000	100	3500	24	35	145,8

The volume of the enterprise's foreign trade turnover was increased by 44.0 percent for A product type and 45.8 percent for B product type compared to the plan.

The analysis of the factors affecting the quantity and size changes can also be evaluated on the basis of the data in the table above.

Compared to the plan, the foreign trade turnover of the enterprise was observed to increase by 22,000 soums for product type A and 11,000 soums for product type B. The effect of these changes can be determined based on the links in the tune.

The influence of factors affecting the change in the gross sales volume of product type A

1. Calculation of the change in the quantity of product A

$$120-100*5000=+10,000 \text{ sums}$$

2. According to the change in the price of product A

$$6000-5000*120=+12.0$$

$$\text{Sum of two factors} = 10.0+12.0=+22.0$$

Factors influencing the change in product size according to the type of product

B

1.B calculation of the change in the amount of product

$$100-80 *3000=+6.0 \text{ thousand sums}$$

B due to the change in the price of the product

$$3500-300*100=5.0 \text{ thousand sums}$$

$$\text{The sum of both factors}=+6.0+5.0=11.0 \text{ thousand sums}$$

All of the above links are negotiable.

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